

ISic0539

I.Sicily inscription 0539

Language

Latin

Type

honorific;

building (?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Erice

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. L(ucius) Seius L(uci) f(ilius) Aem(ila tribu) Fir[---]

2. p pec[---]inpen[---?]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491761

EDCS 22000844

Bibliography

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